

So two rather distinct classes were considered to exist within the population.

Furthermore, transgressive segregation for plant height was observed in the F₂ population of various crosses. The occurrence of transgressive individuals indicates that, besides the major gene, some modifiers control semidwarfism.

Those modifiers may exhibit positive or negative action. Segregation and recombination among modifiers result in the appearance of transgressive individuals.

The segregation between tall and dwarf forms in various crosses, when tested by *chi* square, coincides with a

3:1 ratio (Table 2). That indicates that the semidwarfism of Ai-chiao-nan-te, Ai-tsai-chan. and Dee-geo-woo-gen is largely conditioned by a single pair of recessive genes. Our results agree with IRRI's findings of 1964-65.

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Grain quality

A note on alkali test of rice using a petri dish

Kshirod Ranjan Bhattacharya, Discipline of Rice and Pulse Technology, Central Food Technological Research Institute, Mysore 570013, Karnataka, India

The alkali-degradation test is popular for evaluation of rice quality. In the original method that Little, Hilder, and Dawson developed in 1958, a special plastic box was used in conducting the test. But because the boxes were neither easily available nor essential, researchers generally use a pair of petri dishes instead. The differences in geometry and size, however, require that the volume of KOH solution to use with the petri dish be carefully considered — a point that researchers have often ignored.

Three aspects should be considered: 1) the volume of alkali solution per grain, 2) the depth of alkali in the container, and 3) the surface area available per grain. Attention has usually been paid only to the first aspect, which is erroneous.

The scores of several rice samples in 7-cm-diameter petri dishes were compared with those obtained with the use of the original Little et al (1958) method, the revised Bhattacharya and Sowbhagya (1972) method, and several possible alternatives (see table). The scores in methods IV-A and IV-B were essentially lower than those in the two reference methods (I and II). The scores of the rest were essentially identical. The depth of alkali solution in the container is clearly the crucial factor. Once the

depth is optimal, the volume of alkali per grain can vary fairly widely with no effect.

The other consideration is the available surface area per grain. In the revised procedure of Bhattacharya and Sowbhagya, the total diameter of the degraded grain mass is an important scoring criterion. In the final stages of degradation (scores 5-8), the degraded grain mass assumes a mean diameter of about 20 mm. To score by this method, therefore, sufficient area (πr^2) must be available for each grain to occupy a space of about 3.14 cm². Allowing for vacant intergrain space, that means that a

7-cm-diameter dish can accommodate not more than 7 (or at most 8) grains (see figure). That is why methods I, IV-C, V, and VII gave essentially identical extents of grain degradation, but were nevertheless insufficient for correct scoring of samples showing high degradation. In the limited space available, the collars merged so the correct mass diameter could not be measured.

It was concluded that for interlaboratory comparison using petri dishes of varying sizes for the alkali test, the two essential conditions are: 1) that sufficient alkali solution is added to maintain a liquid depth of 4.5 mm in the

Comparison of alkali test results under different test conditions^a, Karnataka, India.

Testing method	Test condition					Result ^a
	KOH used (ml)	Grains (no.)	Depth of KOH (mm)	MIKOH/grain	Cm ² /grain	
I. Original box method ^b	10	6	4.4	1.7	3.8	(OK)
Petridish methods ^c						
II. Reference method ^d	20	6	5.0	3.3	6.7	OK
III. Excess alkali/grain	20	3	5.0	6.7	13.3	OK
IV. Volume/grain constant						
A	10	6	2.5	1.7	6.7	No
B	15	9	3.8	1.7	4.5	No
C	20	12	5.0	1.7	3.3	(OK)
V. Area/grain constant	20	10	5.0	2.0	4.0	(OK)
VI. KOH depth/grain constant	18	6	4.5	3.0	6.7	OK
VII. Volume, area, depth constant	18	10	4.5	1.8	4.0	(OK)
VIII. Suggested	18	7	4.5	2.5	5.7	OK

^aOK = gives correct score; (OK) = correct at low scores, but incorrect at high scores for the available area is insufficient for optimal spreading; No = score is too low.

^bLittle, Hilder, and Dawson (Cereal Chem. 35, 111, 1958). Plastic box 4.75 × 4.75 × 0.75 cm used. Total area, 23 cm².

^cPetri dish with a 7-cm diameter was used. Total area is 40 cm². Volume refers to that of the alkali solution. Constant means condition identical to that in the original box method.

^dBhattacharya and Sowbhagya (J. Food Technol. 7, 323, 1972).

Bhattacharya alkali test of rice

dish, and 2) that the number of grains per dish should be such as to leave a minimum mean space of 5–6 cm²/grain. Once these conditions are met (it is immaterial if the limits are slightly exceeded), the volume of alkali per grain can be ignored. We have been using reference method II in our routine work. However, alternative VIII might be optimal, because it is closest to the original Little et al method (I) while allowing sufficient space for maximum kernel spreading. ■

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GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Varietal reaction to the kresek phase of bacterial blight

P. Ranga Reddy and Susanta K. Mohanty, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, India

Bacterial blight of rice caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* exhibits two distinct types of symptoms: leaf blight and kresek or wilt. Leaf blight occurs in almost all of rice-growing India. Kresek is occasionally observed in experimental plots and in farmers' fields, particularly in isolated patches. Although kresek is more severe than leaf blight, information on it is limited. Therefore a study was initiated to artificially induce the disease and investigate the susceptibility of some popular rice varieties.

The roots of 15-day-old TN1 seedlings were washed thoroughly. The root tips were finely trimmed with scissors and dipped for 30 minutes in a 48-hour-old bacterial suspension (about 10⁹ cells/ml) grown on potato sucrose agar medium. The treated seedlings were transplanted in pots. Wilting symptoms began to appear 10 days after inoculation and continued appearing up to 20 days, by which time the maximum number of seedlings had collapsed. But not all the inoculated seedlings exhibited kresek; some surviving plants exhibited leaf blight symptoms. Bacteria reisolated from the wilted leaves were confirmed to be *X. oryzae* on the basis of physiological characters and

Reaction of some rice varieties to kresek. Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India.

Varieties	Wilted plants (%)
Lacrosse Zenith/Nira, Nagarbhog	0
BJ1, CO13, Krishna, Zukkoku, Sachikaze, Chinsurah Boro II, Raminad Str. 3, Kanto 51	2.0-8.5
TN1, Jamuna, Malagkit Sungsong, NP125, Cauvery, Kalinga I, Kalinga II, TKM6, Padma	10.0-18.5
IR8, Sigadis, Zenith, IR30, NC1281, Sona, Karuna, IR22, Katna, Kanchi, Rajeswari	22.0-38.5
Pusa 2-21, SLO 16, Jagannath, MTU 17, Supriya, IR24, Semora mangga, Pankaj, Sakti, Vijaya, Jaya	40.0-92.0

pathogenicity on rice plants.

Sixty-four indica and japonica varieties were inoculated using the above method. Ninety-two percent of the plants of the variety Jaya wilted, and 70% of Tadukan and Vijaya plants died. The varieties Lacrosse Zenith/Nira and Nagarbhog showed no wilting symptoms, indicating high kresek resistance. Wilting was minimal (2-6%) in BJ1, Chinsurah Boro II, Krishna, and Zukkoku. But TN1, which is highly susceptible to leaf blight, has only 12% wilting (see table). That indicates that the varietal reaction to the leaf blight phase is not similar to that to the kresek phase. ■

Resistance to sheath blight disease in India

S. Manian and K. Manibhushan Rao, Centre for Advanced Studies in Botany, University of Madras, Madras 600005, India

One hundred and thirty-four entries from the International Rice Sheath Blight Nursery (IRSHBN), 30 cultures from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) program, Hyderabad, and 6 entries from local collections were tested for resistance to sheath blight from March to July 1978 at the Maduravoil Field Research Laboratory, University of Madras, Madras, India. Checks were the resistant IR20, the moderately resistant IR1487-194-5-3-2, and the susceptible Pankaj. The inoculum was autoclaved rice stem cuttings (about 3–4 cm) with 5% dextrose, inoculated with a virulent isolate of *Corticium sasakii* and incubated for 15 days. Among the methods tried, the stem-tape inoculation technique was the most efficient for artificial inoculation. The sheaths of 90-day-old plants were inoculated 5 cm above the water level. They were scored for reaction 12 days later when the disease intensity was maximum in most cultivars.

The following entries were rated as highly resistant and resistant.

Highly resistant: BR4-30-51-2, BR51-49-6, IR2796-44-2, ARC 5925, and ARC 5943.